

Development of a Visual Tool for Carbon Footprint Assessment within an International Collaboration for Sustainability Monitoring

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Abstract

The aim of this article is to create a visual tool for carbon footprint assessment, with the main goal of identifying and selecting crucial sustainability indicators. Carbon footprint monitoring is addressed at global and national scales. Through a structured process, the work proposes to correlate data from countries such as Brazil and Portugal, aiming to define and prioritize the most relevant indicators for tracking corporate carbon footprints. An initial literature review on global and national carbon footprint indicators was conducted. This paper will culminate in the development of an interactive dashboard, allowing for the visualization and calculation of companies' carbon footprints. Ultimately, the study seeks to offer an effective instrument to monitor and analyse the carbon footprint, supporting companies and environmental policies in their sustainability objectives and in the transition to a low-carbon economy.

Keywords: Greenhouse gases; Carbon footprint; ESG.

1 Introduction

The carbon footprint is defined as “the total set of greenhouse gas emissions caused directly and indirectly by an individual, event, organization or product, expressed as CO₂e.” A GHG refers to any gas which accumulates in the atmosphere, absorbs and re-emits heat, thereby carrying the potential for global warming (SIAU, 2021). The carbon footprint includes both carbon emissions released during the combustion of fossil fuels and emissions of other gases, such as methane and nitrous oxide, which also contribute to global warming.

The scientific community, national governments, and global organizations widely agree that unpredictable short- and long-term impacts will arise due to climate change (IPCC, 2021). These impacts will have global effects, directly or indirectly. However, the countries most affected are not necessarily those responsible for producing the highest levels of greenhouse gas emissions or consuming the most non-renewable resources (Mendelsohn et al., 2006; Galli et al., 2014).

Due to growing global concern about environmental issues and the urgent need for sustainable development, governments, organizations, and the scientific community have been directing significant efforts toward achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and, consequently, reducing the carbon footprint in large organizations. These goals, established by the United Nations (UN), aim to promote sustainable economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental protection (United Nations, 2015). In the current context, the carbon footprint has emerged as a key indicator for assessing the impact of human activities on the global climate.

The central objective of this work is the development of a visual tool for carbon footprint measurement. This tool aims to identify and select key sustainability indicators, enabling the effective monitoring of organizations'

carbon footprints, both nationally and internationally. To achieve this purpose and define the most relevant indicators, the study outlines a plan that interlinks national and international approaches. The methodology involves literature review, scientific data collection, and the cross-referencing of information between countries like Brazil and Portugal to classify the main indicators. Understanding these elements is vital for the formulation of public policies and strategies adapted to different socioeconomic contexts (Tsuchiya et al., 2021). The expected outcome is for this tool to support organizations in monitoring their environmental performance, assist in defining emission reduction targets, and foster transparency in environmental management, aligning them with the SDGs and global sustainability targets.

2 Literature Review

This section presents an overview of recent literature and data related to CO₂ emissions, their impacts, and measurement methodologies. It also explores Brazil's emission profile, the alignment with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and the main tools used to calculate the carbon footprint. The goal is to contextualize the development of sustainability indicators and highlight the relevance of carbon footprint assessment in global and national efforts for climate change mitigation.

2.1 Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) Emissions

According to Friedlingstein et al. (2023), atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentrations have shown a continuous increase since 1960, rising from approximately 315 parts per million (ppm) to over 410 ppm by 2020. This steady growth, documented by institutions such as the Scripps Institution of Oceanography and NOAA/ESRL, directly reflects the impact of human activities, particularly the burning of fossil fuels and deforestation. In addition to the overall rise, the data also reveal seasonal variations, highlighting the sensitivity of the carbon cycle to natural and climatic dynamics.

This increase in CO₂ concentrations has significant implications for global warming and climate change. CO₂ is one of the main greenhouse gases, which traps heat in the atmosphere and contributes to rising global temperatures. These measurements reinforce the need for continuous monitoring and strategies to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions to limit future climate change impacts.

This global CO₂ emissions scenario also reflects the Brazilian context, where sectors such as energy, agriculture, and industry play significant roles in GHG emissions. Analyses from the Ministry of Science, Technology, and Innovation (MCTI) on emissions in Brazil show how these activities impact the atmosphere and highlight the country's specific challenges in pursuing sustainable solutions (Brasil, 2013).

According to Makiya and Fraisse (2014), Brazil's greenhouse gas emissions between 1990 and 2010 were largely driven by land use changes, particularly deforestation, which represented the largest share of total emissions throughout the period. Although emissions from the energy, agriculture and livestock, industrial processes, and waste treatment sectors remained relatively stable or grew gradually, emissions linked to forests and land use showed considerable fluctuation, with significant peaks in the mid-1990s and early 2000s, followed by a noticeable decline after 2004.

This analysis is essential for understanding Brazil's emission patterns and guiding public policies aimed at reducing greenhouse gases. Land use and forestry were the primary sources of GHG emissions in Brazil during the analysed period, followed by agriculture and, to a lesser extent, the energy and industrial sectors. The significant impact of land-use changes is mainly related to deforestation in the Amazon and other biomes. However, there has been a downward trend in emissions from this sector in recent years, reflecting efforts to combat deforestation.

On the other hand, sectors such as energy and agriculture have shown stable or increasing contributions, indicating the need for greater attention to these segments. This analysis reinforces the importance of integrated strategies that combine forest protection with advances in energy efficiency, sustainable agricultural practices, and waste management to reduce national emissions and meet international climate commitments.

2.2 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Figure 1 illustrates the main themes related to the SDGs, highlighting the distribution of international results obtained from the Web of Science database. Each rectangle represents a specific SDG, accompanied by a /number that indicates the quantity of studies, projects, or initiatives related to each goal. This analysis provides a comprehensive view of global efforts to promote sustainable development, emphasizing carbon footprint indicators and sustainable practices.

Figure 1. Main Themes Related to the SDGs (WoS, 2024).

The key findings focus on the following SDGs, which have a direct connection to the carbon footprint:

- SDG 9 - Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure (110 results): This goal receives the most attention, emphasizing the importance of developing resilient infrastructure, promoting inclusive and sustainable industrialization, and fostering innovation. Industrialization and innovation play a crucial role in reducing the carbon footprint by adopting clean and efficient technologies.
- SDG 12 - Responsible Consumption and Production (88 results): This goal reflects the focus on sustainable consumption and production practices, which are essential for reducing environmental impact and promoting resource efficiency. The adoption of responsible practices significantly contributes to reducing greenhouse gas emissions.
- SDG 13 - Climate Action (75 results): The emphasis on this goal reinforces the commitment to mitigating climate impacts and tackling climate change. Initiatives focused on climate action are fundamental to reducing the global carbon footprint.

In addition to the highlighted topics, other important SDGs are included in the analysis, even though they are not the primary focus of this study. However, they remain relevant and deserve recognition. These goals emphasize the need for access to affordable, reliable, and sustainable energy, the promotion of decent work and inclusive economic growth, and the development of cities that ensure quality of life and environmental sustainability. They also highlight the conservation of biodiversity in terrestrial and marine ecosystems.

Although these goals are not the primary focus of this study, their inclusion in the analysis demonstrates their importance in the context of sustainable development and carbon footprint mitigation. The analysis indicates

that the main international initiatives and research efforts are focused on innovation, responsible consumption, climate action, and clean energy, reflecting the most urgent and critical themes for sustainable development and carbon footprint reduction.

2.3 Major Carbon Footprint Calculators

Carbon footprint calculators are essential tools for measuring the environmental impact of human activities, helping individuals and organizations understand and reduce their greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. These tools use specific indicators to estimate the amount of carbon emitted directly or indirectly.

For a better analysis of Carbon Footprint indicators, it is essential to understand how these calculations are performed and the categories considered. Table 1 presents a selection of globally used calculators and the input categories for their measurements, based on a compilation originally made by Mulrow et al. (2019).

Table 1. Carbon Footprint Calculator Index by Input Category (Adapted from Mulrow et al., 2019).

Calculator	Home Energy	Transportation	Air Transportation	Food	Water / Wastewater	Extra Categories
Cool Climate Network	Electric, Gas, Oil, Other Fuels	Car, Bus, Train, Inter-City Rail	Short, Medium, Long, Extended	Yes	Water only (based on average)	Purchases (split by goods and services)
Henkel	Electric, Gas, Oil, Coal, Wood, Renewables	Car, Bus, Train, Motorbike, Bike, Walk	Based on km flown	Yes	Based on showers, baths, laundry, dishwasher	Sports, Holiday Travel and Accommodations
WWF	Electric, Gas, Propane, Oil	Car, Motorcycle, Bus, Train	Categories defined by distance from the UK	Yes	No	Miscellaneous
Terrapass	Electric, Gas, Oil, Propane, Gasoline, Diesel	Car, Electric Car, Boat, Train, Bus, Ferry, Taxi	Flight Information: fuel used, total miles, or trip length	No	No	No
IEEE Spectrum	Electric, Gas, Oil	Car	Short, Medium, Continental, Intercontinental	No	No	No
Cleanair Greener	Electric, Gas, Oil	Car	Based on miles flown	No	No	No

Mulrow et al. (2019) presents in their work a set of carbon footprint calculators, from which some examples were selected and adapted in Table 1, classified according to the level of detail (red for low, yellow for moderate and green for high). The categories evaluated include "Home Energy", "Transportation", "Air Transportation", "Food", "Water/Wastewater" and "Extra Categories". Tools such as *Cool Climate Network* and *Henkel* stand out for covering multiple dimensions of the carbon footprint, while others, such as *IEEE Spectrum* and *Cleanair Greener*, have a more restricted scope. This variety highlights the importance of selecting tools compatible with the purpose of the analysis. For example, individuals seeking to reduce their personal environmental impact may benefit from calculators that consider dietary habits and household energy use, while companies interested in reporting emissions or planning broader mitigation actions should prioritize tools that include categories such as corporate transportation, resource use and indirect emissions associated with production activities.

2.4 Project Context within Egalitarian

The Carbon Footprint Project is an initiative developed as part of the Egalitarian project portfolio starting in 2024. The Egalitarian Project is part of the Erasmus initiative, funded with European Union resources and is an

initiative aimed at engaging students from various countries to create sustainable solutions related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Egalitarian, 2025).

In Brazil, teams are primarily focused on solid waste management, where efforts are directed toward prevention, reduction, reuse, and recycling through waste picker cooperatives. However, there was no measurement of these results in terms of carbon dioxide emissions released into the atmosphere. This new approach enables the development of metrics and practical objectives related to the carbon footprint, which can be applied to other projects within the portfolio.

3 Methodology

According to Vergara (2006), applied research aims to solve real-world issues based on established theories. This study is classified as applied research, focusing on measuring the carbon footprint to help companies set carbon footprint reduction targets.

3.1 Research Classification

This is an exploratory study, according to Gil (2002), as it seeks to enhance familiarity with the topic and build hypotheses. The methodology combines systematic bibliographic and qualitative research. The literature review was conducted using the Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar databases, considering contributions from Wackernagel and Rees (1996), pioneers in the ecological footprint concept. Recent approaches to integrating socioeconomic and environmental indicators were analysed.

Indicator selection was based on the criteria of Wiedmann and Minx (2008), prioritizing traceability and comparability. A multi-criteria analysis was applied to rank indicators according to sectoral and regional relevance. The data underwent statistical modelling to measure CO₂ emissions across production chains, following the guidelines of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2019), identifying gaps and opportunities in emissions management.

3.2 Research Structure

The research structure highlights the key analyses and essential components that form the core of the study as a whole. This structure is visually represented in Figure 2. The study was designed based on a set of interconnected objectives and activities, focusing on identifying, prioritizing, and presenting key sustainability indicators, with an emphasis on the carbon footprint. Initially, a global analysis of indicators was conducted, exploring their applicability across different sectors and contexts. This phase included a detailed literature review and a critical analysis of existing indicators, serving as a foundation for the subsequent stages.

Next, a national-level investigation was carried out, focusing on the relevance and applicability of indicators in the local context. This process also began with a literature review and data analysis across various sectors, allowing for an understanding of how these indicators could be utilized in different scenarios.

Figure 2. Research Structure.

Following the identification of indicators, a feasibility and prioritization analysis was conducted based on criteria such as scope, ease of measurement, and impact on environmental policies. Finally, a dashboard was designed for visualizing indicators and calculating the carbon footprint. This included selecting an appropriate

platform, defining an intuitive layout, implementing an indicator-based calculator, and creating a user guide to ensure usability. The dashboards were validated with stakeholders and experts.

4 Results and Discussion

The results were organized into five subsections. The first details the criteria for selecting carbon footprint indicators; the second presents the key indicators; the third analyses their application in carbon footprint calculators; and the last two discuss the development of the dashboard, featuring standardized indicators validated by stakeholders.

4.1 Criteria for Selecting and Identifying Indicators

The measurement of carbon footprint is essential for mitigating environmental impacts, especially in the face of climate change. The SDGs provided guidance for prioritizing relevant, comparable, and sustainability-aligned indicators, such as carbon intensity of GDP and carbon footprint per capita (Gama-Rodrigues et al., 2022). In Brazil, tools like SEEG are crucial for high-impact sectors, such as agriculture and energy (SEEG, 2023).

The selection of indicators should consider scalability and comparability. While transport and energy are global sectors, in Brazil, agriculture and deforestation are the main sources of emissions (Cerri et al., 2017). Using standardized metrics, such as the GHG Protocol and IPCC guidelines, ensures the usefulness of the data (Gama-Rodrigues et al., 2022). Local adaptation is key, considering factors such as methane emissions in livestock and Amazon deforestation (SEEG, 2023). Table 2 presents the selection criteria for indicators, highlighting the most relevant metrics both globally and nationally.

Table 2. Criteria for Carbon Footprint Indicators. (Authors, 2024)

Criteria	Description	Application
Alignment with Objectives	Indicators should be aligned with global SDGs and national targets, such as the Paris Agreement.	Global: Carbon intensity of GDP. National: SEEG targets and carbon regulation.
Sectoral Relevance	Focus on sectors with the greatest environmental impact.	Global: Energy, transport, sustainable consumption. National: Agriculture, land use, energy.
Scalability	Indicators applicable at different levels (local, national, global).	Example: Territorial carbon footprint, export/import, per capita.
Comparability	Metrics that allow comparison between countries or regions.	Example: Indicators based on the GHG Protocol and IPCC guidelines.
Data Availability	Based on reliable sources, accessible, and regularly updated.	Global: Global Footprint Network. National: SEEG, national emissions inventories.
Feasibility of Data Collection	Easy data collection and processing at acceptable costs.	Data at acceptable costs. Indicators using data from public inventories or local estimates.
Regional Flexibility	Adaptable to local and sectoral contexts.	Example: Methane emissions in Brazilian agriculture, regional energy mix.

The strategic choice of carbon footprint indicators is crucial for accurately assessing environmental impacts. By aligning local efforts with global goals, it becomes possible to efficiently monitor GHG emissions and guide public policies and corporate strategies to maximize mitigation.

4.2 Performance Indicators

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) measure whether the actions taken are meeting planned objectives. These indicators are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Ranking of Indicators. (Authors, 2024)

Indicator	Objective	Calculation	Periodicity	Data Collection
Total Carbon Footprint	Measure the total environmental impact of human activities.	Sum of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (tCO ₂ e) from all direct and indirect sources over a given period.	Annual or per project	National inventories, sectoral reports, or data from companies and governmental organizations.
Per Capita Carbon Footprint	Assess the average emissions impact per individual in a region or country.	Division of the total carbon footprint by the number of inhabitants in the studied area.	Annual	Population data and national or regional inventories.
Carbon Intensity of GDP	Relate carbon efficiency to the economic activity of a country or region.	Division of total GHG emissions by the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the analyzed period.	Annual	Official economic reports and GHG emissions inventories.
Emissions by Economic Sector	Identify the most critical sectors in terms of emissions to prioritize mitigation efforts.	Calculation of total emissions for each sector (energy, agriculture, transport, etc.) based on sectoral data.	Annual	Sectoral reports, national inventories, and direct measurements from major emitters.
Emission Scopes (GHG)	Analyse in detail the direct and indirect emissions of organizations.	Classification into Scope 1 (direct), Scope 2 (purchased energy), and Scope 3 (value chain).	Periodic, as needed	Organizational data, such as energy consumption, logistics reports, and operational emissions inventories.
Carbon Footprint of Products and Services	Evaluate the environmental impact of products or services throughout their entire life cycle.	Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), considering everything from raw material extraction to final disposal.	According to the life cycle	Data provided by suppliers, operational reports, and environmental inventories.

Carbon footprint indicators vary in scope and applicability:

- Total Carbon Footprint provides a general overview of greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) in a region.
- Per Capita Carbon Footprint highlights average emissions per inhabitant, useful for country comparisons.
- GDP Carbon Intensity assesses carbon efficiency in relation to economic growth.
- Sectoral Analysis identifies critical areas such as energy and transportation for mitigation efforts.

Additionally, the GHG Protocol (2025) structures emissions into three scopes:

- Scope 1 - Direct emissions from controlled sources.
- Scope 2 - Indirect emissions from purchased energy.
- Scope 3 - Indirect emissions from the value chain.

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is widely used to calculate the carbon footprint of products and services, evaluating emissions across all stages of the production cycle, from raw material extraction to disposal. These indicators guide sustainable policies and strategies, promoting emission reduction and transforming global practices.

4.3 Dashboard

As the main database for the creation of the dashboard, data from two companies in Portugal were used, one from the construction sector (Company 1) and another from the textile sector (Company 2), both with their identities preserved. The provided data include the consumption of acquired energy for both companies, as well as water consumption and waste generation for the construction company. Data on emissions from the use of machinery powered by natural gas, electricity, and maritime transport were also considered.

The collected data were compiled into the interactive dashboard, developed in Power BI, providing a clear and dynamic visualization of the carbon emissions of both companies. It is possible to monitor and analyse environmental metrics in detail, such as energy consumption, water usage, waste generation, and emissions from different sources. Additionally, strategic insights can be generated, enabling more informed decision-making, promoting transparency, and enhancing efficiency in carbon footprint management.

Figures 3 and 4 present images of the developed dashboard.

Figure 3. Dashboard of Company 1 (Civil Construction).

Figure 4. Dashboard of Company 2 (Textile Industry).

The combination of dashboards and carbon calculators strengthens companies' environmental management. While dashboards provide a clear and interactive view of the data, calculators help estimate greenhouse gas emissions based on different indicators. Together, these tools make it easier to monitor, simulate scenarios, and make more sustainable decisions, making carbon footprint management more efficient and transparent.

5 Conclusion

The Carbon Footprint Project has successfully established a robust methodology for identifying and prioritizing key carbon footprint indicators at both global and national levels, exemplified by the cross-referencing of data between Brazil and Portugal. This approach, informed by a thorough literature review and validated by stakeholders, has paved the way for the development of practical tools for monitoring and analysing carbon emissions. The project's focus on alignment with SDGs and global environmental policies ensures the relevance and applicability of the selected indicators for driving sustainability efforts.

The ongoing development of an interactive dashboard, demonstrated through the initial integration of data from Portuguese companies, signifies a tangible outcome of the project. This dashboard promises to be an effective tool for visualizing environmental metrics and calculating companies' carbon footprints, thereby supporting informed decision-making and promoting transparency. Ultimately, the Carbon Footprint Project contributes significantly to the broader goals of the Egalitarian initiative by providing a framework for measuring and managing environmental impact, aiding companies and policymakers in achieving their sustainability objectives and contributing to a global transition towards a lower-carbon economy.

The study successfully achieved its main objectives by identifying and prioritizing key carbon footprint indicators and developing a functional dashboard capable of visualizing and calculating emissions data. These tools support organizations in monitoring their environmental performance and aligning with international sustainability goals. However, the research faced some limitations, such as the restricted availability of standardized data from different sectors and regions, as well as operational inconsistencies in some online calculators during the testing phase. Future studies could expand the analysis by incorporating data from a broader range of industries and countries, as well as exploring the integration of real-time data collection systems and machine learning techniques to enhance predictive capabilities and automate sustainability reporting.

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References

- Brasil. Ministério de Ciência, Tecnologia e Informação (2013). Estimativas anuais de emissões de gases de efeito estufa no Brasil. Available at https://repositorio.mcti.gov.br/bitstream/mctic/4303/1/2013_estimativas_anuais_emissoes_gases_efeito_estufa_brasil.pdf. Accessed 19 Nov 2024.
- Cerri, C. E. P., You, X., Cherubin, M. R., Moreira, C. S., Raucci, G. S., Castiglioni B. A., Alves, P. A., Cerri, D. G. P., Mello, F. F. C., Cerri, C. C. (2017). Assessing the greenhouse gas emissions of Brazilian soybean biodiesel production. *PLoS One*, v. 12, n. 5, p. e0176948, 2017. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0176948>. Accessed 1 Nov 2024.
- Egalitarian. Context. 2025. Available at <https://egalitarian.eu/about/main-context>. Accessed 1 Nov 2024.
- Ferreira, J. P., Marques, J. L., Pires, S. M., Iha, K., & Galli, A. (2023). Supporting national-level policies for sustainable consumption in Portugal: A socio-economic Ecological Footprint analysis. *Ecological Economics*, 205, 107687. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107687>. Accessed 19 Nov 2024.

- Friedlingstein, P., O'Sullivan, M., Jones M. W., Andrew R. M. et al. (2023). Global Carbon Budget 2023. Earth System Science Data. Available at <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-15-5301-2023>. Accessed 19 Nov 2024.
- Galli, A., Wackernagel, M., IHA, K., Lazarus, E. (2014). Ecological Footprint: Implications for Biodiversity. Biological Conservation, v. 173, p. 121–132, 2014. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2013.10.019>. Accessed 19 Nov 2024.
- Gama-Rodrigues, E. F., Gama-Rodrigues, A. C., Vicente, L. C., Alvarenga, L. C. B. R., Muller, M. W., Partelli, F. L., Gonçalves, J. L. M., Freitas, L. S., Alvaristo, D. M., Cruz, I. B., Souza, I. S. G., Faitanin, M. A. (2022). Perspectives on carbon footprint of agricultural land-use in Brazil. Carbon Footprints, v. 1, p. 1-12, 2022. Available at <https://doi.org/10.20517/cf.2022.01>. Accessed 19 Nov 2024.
- Gil, A. C. (2002). Como elaborar projetos de pesquisa. São Paulo: Atlas.
- IPCC – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. (2019). 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories. Kanagawa: IPCC. Available at <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/2019-refinement-to-the-2006-ipcc-guidelines-for-national-greenhouse-gas-inventories/>. Accessed 1 Nov 2024.
- IPCC – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. (2021). Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Geneva: IPCC. Available at <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/>. Accessed 1 Nov 2024.
- Makiya, I. K., Fraise, C. W. (2014). Sustainability initiatives driving supply chain: climate governance on beef production system. Journal of Technology Management & Innovation, v. 10, n. 1, p. 215–224, 2015. Available at <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0718-27242015000100016>. Accessed 19 Nov 2024.
- Mendelsohn, R., Dinar, A., Williams, L. (2006). The distributional impact of climate change on rich and poor countries. Environment and Development Economics, v. 11, n. 2, p. 159-178. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1355770X05002755>. Accessed 1 Nov 2024.
- Mulrow, J., Machaj, K., Deanes, J., Derrible, S. (2019). The state of carbon footprint calculators: An evaluation of calculator design and user interaction features. Sustainable Production and Consumption, v. 16, p. 1-12. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2018.12.001>. Accessed 1 Nov 2024.
- SEEG. (2023). SEEG Brazil – The Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Removals Estimation System. SEEG. Available at <https://seeg.eco.br/>. Accessed 19 Nov 2024.
- Siau, K., Hayee, B., Gayam, S. (2021). Endoscopy's current carbon footprint. Techniques and Innovations in Gastrointestinal Endoscopy, v. 23, n. 4, p. 344-352, 2021. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tige.2021.06.005>. Accessed 1 Nov 2024.
- Silva, V. P. R., Aleixo, D. O., Almeida, R. S. R., Campos, J. H. B. C., Araujo, L. E. (2015). Modelo integrado das pegadas hídrica, ecológica e de carbono para o monitoramento da pressão humana sobre o planeta. Ambiente Guarapuava (PR), v. 11, n. 3, p. 639-649. Available at <https://doi.org/10.5935/ambiencia.2015.03.09>. Accessed 1 Nov 2024.
- Tsuchiya, K., Iha, K., Murthy, A., Lin, D. et al. (2021). Decentralization & local food: Japan's regional Ecological Footprints indicate localized sustainability strategies. Journal of Cleaner Production, v. 292, e126043, 2021. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126043>. Accessed 19 Nov 2024.
- United Nations. (2015). Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Available at <https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/publications/21252030%20Agenda%20for%20Sustainable%20Development%20web.pdf>. Accessed 1 Nov 2024.
- Vergara, S. C. (2006). Projetos e relatórios de pesquisa. São Paulo: Atlas.
- Wackernagel, M., Rees, W. (1996). Our ecological footprint: Reducing human impact on the Earth. Philadelphia: New Society Publishers, 1996.
- Wiedmann, T., Minx, J. (2008). A Definition of 'Carbon Footprint'. In: Pertsova, C. C. (Ed.). Ecological Economics Research Trends. Nova Science Publishers, Inc.
- World Resources Institute, & World Business Council for Sustainable Development. (2025). GHG Protocol – Greenhouse Gas Protocol. Available at <https://www.wri.org/initiatives/greenhouse-gas-protocol>. Accessed 19 Nov 2024.